

Deliverable D19.1

Deployable Demonstrator of Digital Objects & Workflows Developments

Project Title (Grant agreement number)	EOSC-ENTRUST Grant Agreement 101131056		
Project Acronym (EC call)	EOSC-ENTRUST		
WP No & Title	WP19: Trusted research environment blueprint - Establishing a common terminology and approach		
WP Leaders	Salvador Capella (BSC), Philip Quinlan (UNOTT)		
Deliverable Lead Beneficiary	BSC, UNOTT		
Contractual delivery date	30/11/2024	Actual date	29/11/2024
Delayed	No		
Partner(s) contributing to this deliverable	BSC, UNOTT, UNIMAN		
Authors	Philip Quinlan (UNOTT) https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3012-6646 Laia Codó (BSC) https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6797-8746 Jonathan Couldridge (UNOTT) https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4054-1146 Eugenio Gonzalo (BSC) https://orcid.org/0009-0009-5133-3204 Stian Soiland-Reyes (UNIMAN) https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9842-9718 Jose M ^a Fernandez (BSC) https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4806-5140 Tim Beck (UNOTT) https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0292-7972		
Contributors	Carole Goble (UNIMAN) https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1219-2137		

Acknowledgements (not grant participants)	Eli Chadwick (UNIMAN) https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0035-6475 Paula Iborra (BSC) https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0504-3029
Reviewers	Rob Baxter (HDR UK/DARE UK) https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3693-8725 Pal Saetrom (NTNU) https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8142-7441 Anne Van der Kant (Health RI) https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5802-7076

Log of changes

Date	Mvm	Who	Description
25/10/2024		Stian Soiland-Reyes [SSR], Laia Codó [LC], Eugenio Gonzalo [EG]	Structured document
04/11/2024		Jonathan Couldridge [JC], Stian Soiland-Reyes [SSR] Jose M ^a Fernandez [JF]	Sections 4.1 & 4.3
11/11/2024		Laia Codó [LC]	1st draft for sections 3 & 4
13/11/2024		Philip Quinlan [PQ], Jonathan Couldridge [JC], Laia Codó [LC], Eugenio Gonzalo [EG]	version 1.0

Disclaimer

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. This deliverable is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.

Table of contents

1. Executive Summary	4
2. Contribution towards project objectives	4
Objective 1	4
Objective 2	5
Objective 3	6
Objective 4	6
3. Methods	7
3.1. Delivery Scope	7
3.2. Methodology	8
4. Description of work accomplished	9
4.1. Background	9
4.1.1. Interoperability Standards	9
RO-Crate	9
GA4GH Task Execution Service (TES)	11
GA4GH Beacon	11
4.1.2. Existing Implementations	12
Data and Analytics Research Environments UK (DARE UK)	12
TRE-FX	13
Five Safes RO-Crate	13
Health Data Research (HDR) UK Cohort Discovery Tool	18
WfExS-backend	18
4.1.3. TRE-FX setup	19
Beacon implementation	21
HDR UK implementation	21
Deployment	21
4.1.4. Gap Analysis	22
4.1.5. WfExS-backend Extension	25
4.2. Future Architecture view	26
4.2.1. Mapping to EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint	28
5. Results	30
6. Discussion	31
7. Next steps	32
8. Impact	32
I. Appendix: Results	33

1. Executive Summary

The rapid growth of federated¹ tools, platforms, analytics and learning approaches are revolutionising data analysis by enabling insights without the need to consolidate data files in a single location. Such approaches hold the potential to scale analyses significantly. However, the challenge lies in how Trusted Research Environments (TREs) can support this constantly evolving analytical landscape. Building a future-proof blueprint based on any single federated tool, platform, or technique is unrealistic. Instead, we must explore how existing international standards can act as adaptable frameworks.

The Digital Objects & Workflows Demonstrator aims to evidence the power of these standards and middleware to integrate multiple federated platforms and analytics through a single software installation. By providing practical evidence, this work informs the blueprint design for TREs. Our work has developed a functional module for secure and interoperable workflow execution within TREs, addressing the growing need for standardised, FAIR²-compliant computational analyses across federated compute infrastructures.

By building on the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint's architecture components and aligning closely with standards from the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH) and the Five Safes RO-Crate, WP19 seeks to demonstrate how workflows can be managed and executed in TREs in a secure and reproducible manner while ensuring data sovereignty.

2. Contribution towards project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives/key results:

	Key Result No and description	Contributed
Objective 1 Create a European network of Trusted Research Environments, linked to EOSC	1. A catalogue of suitable national or institutional TREs as part of the EOSC offering (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15)	No
	2. A 'starter pack' of exemplar projects to demonstrate how networks of TREs can address European research priorities (WP4/5/6, WP7/8/9)	No
	3. European researchers are aware of capabilities through communication and outreach events (WP4/5/6)	No

¹ See [EOSC-ENTRUST Architecture Glossary](#)

² FAIR: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable, <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles>

and EuroHPC, to enable transnational collaborative research on sensitive or restricted data.	and materials delivered to support national TRE training programmes (WP4/5/6, WP13/14/15)	
	4. Enable federated use via standards and technology for trusted researcher identity, data use and data access linked to developing European framework for trusted electronic identification of individuals (WP16/17/18)	No
	5. Enable researchers and software developers to deploy across multiple TREs via secure FAIR digital objects and workflows (WP16/17/18, WP19/20/21)	Yes
	6. EuroHPC capacity that meets the need for secure exascale and GPU (e.g., AI) computing can be identified and connected using the EOSC-ENTRUST framework (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15).	No
Objective 2 Trusted Research Environment providers implement, validate, and promote their capabilities through a European framework using common standards and shared legal, operational and technical language.	1. An established European network of national and institutional TRE Providers (WP10/11/12)	No
	2. A service blueprint that allows technical interoperability between TRE based on the EOSC Interoperability framework (WP13/14/15)	Yes
	3. National and institutional TREs consistently set out their capabilities with common representation for validated legal, operational, semantics and technical aspects (WP10/11/12).	No
	4. Define the security baseline and auditing procedures for TREs to support the Five Safes ³ principles and capture requirements in guidelines for FAIR sensitive data in EOSC (WP13/14/15, WP19/20/21)	Yes
	5. Drive TRE composability via policy and process interoperability and set out an EOSC compliant governance model for a TRE services network (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15).	No

³ Elizabeth Green et al. The present and future of the {Five Safes} framework. Nov. 2023, doi: 10.29012/jpc.831

<p>Objective 3</p> <p>National funders and governments understand the network of TRE capabilities serving their needs, and how TREs support their national priorities and their contributions to selected transnational programmes</p>	<p>1. A machine-readable catalogue of TRE capabilities allowing detailed, comparative analysis of technical capabilities and identification of gaps (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15).</p>	No
	<p>2. Policy briefs on the capabilities of the European TRE Provider Forum (WP4/5/6, WP10/11/12) and Use Cases of their application in research domains of high societal impact (WP7/8/9).</p>	No
	<p>3. Connection between the EOSC-ENTRUST Provider Forum and the European Data Spaces (WP1/2/3, WP4/5/6).</p>	No
<p>Objective 4</p> <p>The European Network of Trusted Research Environments (EOSC-ENTRUST) is embedded in the European Open Science Cloud and the European Data Spaces and fosters an ecosystem of public, private and joint-venture providers of TRE services.</p>	<p>1. National and organisational providers are incorporated into EOSC via national members and the European network forms part of EOSC long-term strategy (WP1/2/3, WP4/5/6).</p>	No
	<p>2. The emerging European Data Spaces build their capabilities on the network of existing and developing TRE providers (WP4/5/6).</p>	No
	<p>3. Technological developments required by one Data Space activity can be directed to a forum of TRE specialists, reducing the need for duplication and coordinating investment in foundational technologies (WP10/11/12).</p>	No
	<p>4. A driver project to demonstrate opportunities for public-private partnerships (WP7/8/9)</p>	No

3. Methods

3.1. Delivery Scope

The goal of this deliverable is to provide a working demonstrator to the ENTRUST programme so that we can evidence the power of existing open source, standards driven approaches to federated analytics and federated learning. The key outcome of the Demonstrator is to influence future designs, to spot the gaps of current approaches and use it as a tool to engage the wider EOSC-ENTRUST programme.

From this initial Demonstrator our objectives were:

- To demonstrate how an existing install of the DARE UK⁴ prototype, built from open source and standards-based components, ensures that a TRE can be a member of two entirely different federated discovery platforms, the GA4GH Beacon⁵ and the HDR UK Cohort Discovery tool⁶.
- To identify the gaps in the current approach and to test the acceptability of the approach with the emerging ENTRUST architecture.
- To understand the deployment mechanisms for a TRE and the various types of TREs represented in the TRE Providers forum.
- To evidence the benefits of adopting existing international standards over designing new federated protocols.

The deliverable outlines several key achievements:

- A demonstration of interoperability between WfExS-backend⁷ and TRE-FX⁸ from DARE UK, showcasing how a TRE can participate in federated discovery networks like HDR UK Cohort Discovery and GA4GH Beacon.
- A comprehensive gap analysis, identifying necessary changes to support the future deployment and enhance system capabilities.
- Introduction of the latest release of WfExS-backend, the workflow orchestrator central to this approach.
- A target design that captures feedback from the early EOSC-ENTRUST blueprints (WP13), the strategic drivers (WP7) and TRE providers (WP10).

⁴ DARE-UK: Data and Analytics Research Environments United Kingdom, <https://dareuk.org.uk/>

⁵ GA4GH beacon, <https://www.ga4gh.org/product/beacon-api/>

⁶ HDR UK Cohort Discovery tool, <https://www.hdruk.ac.uk/news/hdruk-launches-transformational-new-search-functionality-cohort-discovery/>

⁷ Jose. M Fernández, et al. FAIR Workflow Execution with WfExS and Workflow Run Crate. BioHackEU23, 28 March 2024, doi: [10.37044/osf.io/7f94w](https://doi.org/10.37044/osf.io/7f94w)

⁸ Thomas Giles, et al. TRE-FX: Delivering a Federated Network of Trusted Research Environments to Enable Safe Data Analytics. Zenodo, 30 octubre 2023, doi: [10.5281/zenodo.10055354](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10055354).

3.2. Methodology

Demonstrator

The approach to the deliverable was to create a fully functional Demonstrator built on the existing work of previous programs and enhancing it. By undertaking this initial deliverable, we compare the Demonstrator to the key criteria emerging from the other work packages in EOSC-ENTRUST. Most important is to demonstrate how a single installation can support multiple federated platforms and standards. In doing so, it has immense value to the blueprint as we understand what components can be generic and to test the design patterns.

This document introduces the first version of the Demonstrator, which will continue to be developed over the coming two years. Future iterations will incorporate lessons from the current setup and feedback from use cases to further refine and optimise its functionality.

Future Architecture design

A preliminary design for the next Demonstrator is included in this document. This design considers alignment with EOSC-ENTRUST drivers' functional requirements, the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint architecture, and the EOSC-ENTRUST TRE providers group to ensure it meets the technical needs and constraints of TREs. [Figure 1](#) summarises the inputs and contributions considered for the Demonstrator design of the next year.

Figure 1: Next Release Demonstrator design rationale. Diagram details inputs incorporated (blue boxes) in the subsequent conceptual design phases (orange boxes) of the Demonstrator.

The following outlines the key design principles applied:

- **Requirements Alignment:** WP19 validates that design aligns with technical and operational needs from project drivers and TRE providers, following the Initial Driver Requirements report⁹, and placing particular emphasis on interoperability and federation requirements. The goal is to enable federated analytics and learning flows in a modular and customizable architectural manner, facilitating future adoption.
- **Blueprint Architecture Alignment:** For federated environments, WP19 maps architectural specifications taken for the first Blueprint release¹⁰ onto Demonstrator components to create a high-level unified data access and analysis framework.
- **Interoperability Standards:** To meet interoperability challenges in federated systems, WP19 adopts established research and industry standards, introduced and discussed in [Interoperability Standards](#) section.
- **Existing Software Integration:** The Demonstrator builds on [established software solutions](#), enabling faster prototyping of a deployable module.

4. Description of work accomplished

The deliverable was focused on the re-use of an existing software stack and standards. They were individually developed but assembled into a single Demonstrator in ENTRUST.

4.1. Background

This section provides an overview of key interoperability standards that facilitate workflow environments across TREs. It will also describe existing software solutions specifically designed to manage task executions in isolated environments, addressing challenges in secure data sharing, task management and workflow orchestration.

4.1.1. Interoperability Standards

RO-Crate

Research Object Crate (RO-Crate¹¹) is a community-developed method for FAIR packaging of research data with structured metadata, building on established Web standards¹², used

⁹ EOSC-ENTRUST Milestone M7.1: [Initial Driver Requirements for TREs from the four Drivers](#)

¹⁰ EOSC-ENTRUST Deliverable D13.4: [Year one version of EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint & Interoperability Framework](#)

¹¹RO-Crate, <https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/>

¹² Stian Soiland-Reyes, et al. Packaging research artefacts with RO-Crate. 1 Jan. 2022: 97–138, 2022, doi: [10.3233/DS-210053](https://doi.org/10.3233/DS-210053)

in a multitude of domains¹³. For workflow execution provenance the Workflow Run Crate profile (WRROC)¹⁴ has been implemented by multiple workflow engines, shown in [Table 1](#):

Table 1. List of Workflow Run RO-Crate implementations, adapted from <https://www.researchobject.org/workflow-run-crate/#implementations--examples>

WRROC implementation	Profile	Example RO-Crate
runcrate	Provenance	10.5281/zenodo.7774351
Galaxy	Workflow	10.5281/zenodo.7785861
COMPSs	Workflow	10.5281/zenodo.7788030
StreamFlow	Provenance	10.5281/zenodo.7911906
WfExS-backend	Workflow	10.5281/zenodo.10091550
Sapporo	Workflow	10.5281/zenodo.10134581
Autosubmit	Workflow	10.5281/zenodo.8144612
Nextflow	Provenance	example

RO-Crate has also been highlighted as an enabler of FAIR Computational Workflows, an area being developed by the EuroScienceGateway project with WorkflowHub registry¹⁵.

The Workflows Community Initiative¹⁶ has recently formulated the requirements of FAIR Computational Workflows¹⁷, including the concept of workflow components, which in EOSC-ENTRUST has been highlighted by the need for further details of software containers used by workflow (e.g. ensuring the container is built from reliable open source software before permitting it inside the TRE environment).

The main purpose of RO-Crate, as used by humanities and digital libraries communities, is to add context to the data and give evidence of its creation, e.g. for attribution and trust. In EOSC-ENTRUST, this means not just to document computational processing in TREs, but also the Five Safes Framework's aspects of Safe Data, Safe Projects, Safe People, Safe Settings and Safe Outputs¹⁸.

¹³ RO-Crate in use, https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/use_cases

¹⁴ Simone Leo et al. Recording provenance of workflow runs with RO-Crate. 9) 10 Sep. 2024, doi: [10.1371/journal.pone.0309210](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0309210)

¹⁵ Stian Soiland-Reyes et al. EuroScienceGateway D2.1: Reproducible FAIR Digital Objects for Workflows. Zenodo, 28 Ago. 2024, doi: [10.5281/zenodo.13225792](https://zenodo.org/record/13225792).

¹⁶ Workflows Community Initiative: <https://workflows.community/>

¹⁷ Wilkinson et al. Applying the FAIR Principles to Computational Workflows. arXiv 2410.03490 <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2410.03490>

¹⁸ Elizabeth Green et al. The present and future of the {Five Safes} framework. Nov. 2023, doi: [10.29012/jpc.831](https://doi.org/10.29012/jpc.831)

GA4GH Task Execution Service (TES)

The GA4GH Task Execution Service (TES)¹⁹ is an API specification developed by the GA4GH to provide a standardised way of submitting, managing, and monitoring tasks or jobs (like running workflows) across different compute environments.

GA4GH TES allows researchers to run tasks across various platforms, cloud providers, and compute environments in a standardised way. By using TES, workflow managers and compute engines can interact seamlessly with diverse backends, making it easier to execute tasks in a distributed and heterogeneous environment. This enables interoperability in the execution layer, as any system compliant with the TES API can submit, manage, and monitor tasks, facilitating cross-platform and cross-institutional compatibility.

The GA4GH TES specification is designed to work in tandem with other GA4GH standards, like the Workflow Execution Service (WES)²⁰, the Data Repository Service (DRS)²¹ or the Tools Registry Service (TRS)²². TRS enables the registration, querying, and retrieval of tools and workflows through a standardised API, which can be accessed by services like WES or TES nodes. Nodes implementing GA4GH WES are meant to orchestrate the execution of multi-step workflows by breaking them into individual tasks and delegating each task to trusted TES nodes for execution. A TES node deploys requested tasks on its underlying compute layout, and could leverage GA4GH DRS (along with other industrial standards, like S3²³ or WebDAV²⁴) to retrieve and store data required for and produced by each requested task. Services implementing GA4GH DRS provide standardised data location resolution and access through unique identifiers (DRS URIs), allowing both TES and WES nodes which support them to finally access input data consistently and register outputs regardless of the underlying storage infrastructure.

GA4GH Beacon

The Beacon API specification is developed by the GA4GH as an open standard for the discovery of genomic and phenoclinical data in biomedical research applications. The original version 1 of the API supported boolean responses (yes/no) to queries about the presence of a specified genetic variant in a dataset that had ‘lit’ a beacon. Version 2 of the API specification is significantly more adaptable, offering greater flexibility and query richness. It allows for returning both records and counts, allowing for the discovery of variants, individuals and biosamples by enabling queries based on genomic coordinates,

¹⁹ GA4GH Task Execution Service (TES), <https://ga4gh.github.io/task-execution-schemas>

²⁰ Workflow Execution Service (WES), <https://ga4gh.github.io/workflow-execution-service-schemas>

²¹ Data Repository Service (DRS), <https://ga4gh.github.io/data-repository-service-schemas>

²² Tools Registry Service (TRS), <https://ga4gh.github.io/tool-registry-service-schemas>

²³ Amazon S3, <https://aws.amazon.com/s3/>

²⁴ WebDAV, <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/html/rfc4918>

clinical findings and technical (meta)data²⁵. The use of Beacon ‘filters’ enables the querying of parameters such as phenotypes, disease codes and demographic data.

Beacon is organised into two parts: the Beacon Framework and the Beacon Model. The Beacon Framework describes the common components applicable to all Beacons and is agnostic to the implementation domain. It defines features such as endpoints, structure of query requests and responses, filters and handovers. The Beacon Models are tailored to suit specific user communities and describe the domain entities (e.g., individuals, cohorts, biosamples) and the relationships between them. Beacon works alongside other clinical data standards, such as Phenopackets, OMOP and FHIR. A Beacon implementation is able to return matches in a beacon response and provide a handover to other data exchange formats used by the implementing service.

Data services that have been 'beaconised' represent an enhancement in data discoverability with minimal risks. Authorised users can make a broad range of queries, from positional requests for genomic variations in datasets (v1 & v2) to clinical and biomedical queries (v2).

4.1.2. Existing Implementations

Data and Analytics Research Environments UK (DARE UK)

The vision of DARE UK is for all research and innovation to benefit from seamless, secure use of diverse sensitive data, at a pace, efficiency and scale approaching that of the open data ecosystem, that revolutionises research productivity and accelerates research to deliver public good. The mission is UK focused and set out as to put the UK at the forefront of sensitive data research and innovation by assembling the tools, technologies and standards needed to streamline secure data linkage and use.

During 2023 it funded several sprint programmes to assess the current state of the possible in terms of emerging needs of the research community. One of those projects to be funded was a mechanism to deliver federated analytics using existing open source tooling. The project called TRE-FX created some initial components, set out below.

²⁵ Jordi Rambla, et al. Beacon v2 and Beacon networks: A "lingua franca" for federated data discovery in biomedical genomics, and beyond. Human mutation, June 2022, doi: [10.1002/humu.24369](https://doi.org/10.1002/humu.24369)

TRE-FX

TRE-FX²⁶ serves as the baseline implementation for the current Demonstrator. This section highlights the primary implementation, but for in-depth technical details, please consult the Technical Documentation²⁷.

The Primary TRE-FX implementation is a modular architecture designed to integrate securely within TREs, with flexibility to use interchangeable components. It runs on three individual host computers and includes an API-based structure composed of key components - the Submission Layer, TRE Controller, and Workflow Executor - supported by additional services such as Keycloak for authentication and an intermediary store (MINIO²⁸) for data handling.

Key Components:

- **Submission Layer:** Within TRE-FX positioned outside the TREs, this layer is the first interface for incoming analytical tasks via an GA4GH TES API. It validates the request and then queues tasks submitted by users or software vendors through a User Portal and GA4GH TES API.
- **TRE Controller:** Located within the TREs, this component polls out to pull down any jobs for the TRE sat in the Submission Layer queue. The TRE-Controller includes a UI for managing tasks, logs, and metrics that can be accessed by TRE staff.
- **Workflow Execution Layer:** Within TRE-FX, this was within the TREs, and performed by Hutch. It receives the request from the Controller to process a job, and prepares the Crate and workflow before initiating WfExS-backend (see section [WfExS-backend](#)), to run the workflow.

Five Safes RO-Crate

The TRE-FX project²⁹ utilise the Five Safes RO-Crate profile³⁰ for documenting and informing processing of computational analyses in TREs, across phases shown in [Figure 2](#):

²⁶ Dr Thomas Giles et al. TRE-FX: Delivering a Federated Network of Trusted Research Environments to Enable Safe Data Analytics. Zenodo, Oct 2023, doi: [10.5281/zenodo.10055354](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10055354).

²⁷ Thomas Giles et al. TRE-FX Technical Documentation - Primary Implementation. Zenodo, Jan. 2024, doi: [10.5281/zenodo.10376657](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10376657)

²⁸ MINIO, <https://min.io>

²⁹ TRE-FX project, <https://trefx.uk/>

³⁰ Soiland-Reyes, S., et al. TRE-FX Technical Documentation - Five Safes Ro-crate. 0.4, Zenodo, 14 de diciembre de 2023, doi: [10.5281/zenodo.10376350](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10376350)

Figure 2: Phases of Five Safes RO-Crate for workflow execution. Adapted from <https://trefx.uk/>

These phases³¹ document the processing stages of a trusted research environment:

- **Check Phase** – the crate is checked for integrity and completeness before passing to the TRE.
- **Validation Phase** – The crate metadata is checked for validity according to the profile.
- **Workflow Retrieval Phase** – TRE retrieves the requested workflow, typically from a local proxy of pre-approved workflows.
- **Sign-off Phase** – TRE verifies the requesting user/project is permitted to execute the given workflow on the TRE's data. This may include manual inspection e.g. selection criteria in input parameters.
- **Workflow Execution Phase** – TRE records execution of the workflow using a workflow engine, recording results and any errors.
- **Disclosure Phase** – The Crate goes through disclosure control before leaving the TRE – this may be manual or semi-automatic depending on the workflow.
- **Publishing Phase** – The Crate is made ready for publishing outside of the TRE and delivery to the user and data usage registers.
- **Receiving Phase** – The client or data usage register may check the returned Crate for completeness of the above phases and record this.

The TRE-FX architecture is used by HDR UK for federated analytics, and forms a starting point for EOSC-ENTRUST not just for WfExS-backend and Hutch but also for other computational analysis. The Five Safes are mapped in the following table:

³¹ TRE-FX project documentation, <https://trefx.uk/5s-crate/#phases-of-five-safes-ro-crate>

Table 2: RO-Crate metadata in Five Safes Framework. Adapted from³²

Dimension	RO-Crate metadata
Safe data	Requested input parameters: to the pre-approved workflow that will execute against the TRE eligible data projection/portion with pre-approved, confidential-safe data
Safe projects	Responsible project: The project that the request is sent on behalf of, related to permission to use a TRE.
Safe people	Requesting Agent: The individual person who is requesting the workflow run and the organisation they are representing for access control purposes.
Safe settings	Requested Workflow Run: Pre-approved workflow pre-installed on the TRE.
Safe outputs	Output entities: described as a Workflow Run Crate profile with workflow provenance and aggregated results for disclosure control inspection.

Our initial work in EOSC-ENTRUST is based on expanding the support for the Five Safe Crates in the WfExS-backend workflow execution service and in the TRE-FX architecture to fully support the contextual descriptions indicated above.

Air Gap principle

A common principle in TREs in the UK is the implementation of an air gap – a physical or network isolation mechanism— between the researcher and the data. The researcher will first login to the TRE, and then be provided a virtual environment where they will be able to access the data. In this virtual environment there will be no internet access, they cannot bring in data nor extract data without the permission of the TRE. This principle is a cornerstone of many TREs and allows them to provide assurance that no sensitive or confidential data is leaving the TRE.

A key task within the DARE UK work in TRE-FX was to demonstrate that federated analytics could be facilitated and parts of the process are automated, but without compromising on the principle of the air gap.

The consequence to the design is that this means workflows, crates, containers cannot be simply retrieved on the fly from the outside world, as the environment where the data will be held and where the analytics performed will not have internet access.

³² Stian Soiland-Reyes et al. Five Safes RO-Crate: FAIR Digital Objects for Trusted Research Environments. FDO 2024 (proceedings under review)

<https://research.manchester.ac.uk/en/publications/five-safes-ro-crate-fair-digital-objects-for-trusted-research-env>

Process for handling a query

Figure 3: Captures the main three components of the TRE-FX architecture which is the Submission Layer, TRE Controller Layer and TRE Executor Layer. The separation of tasks is that the submission layer receives the TES payload for a network of TREs and places these in TRE specific queues. Each TRE requires a TRE Controller Layer that can access the Submission Layer, and submit the job for processing in the Executor Layer.

The TRE-FX stack was designed to demonstrate the feasibility of the approach and [Figure 3](#) captures the key components within the TRE-FX stack. The expected process is that prior to submitting a new task to run across a federation of TREs, a researcher will have applied and got approval from all TREs involved. This is an important stage, as it also allows the TRE Admin to pre-configure the Workflow Executor Layer for the particular project. The project is then registered by the TREs within the Submission Layer, therefore it has an entry for a project that has been approved and what TREs have approved.

Equally at this time, the TRE prepares the Workflow Executor Layer to cater for the airgap. They will pre-fetch the workflow from the required repository, in our example, Workflow Hub, and place this in the Nexus filestore ([Figure 3](#), component G) and they will collect the required container images and place this in a local container store ([Figure 3](#), component I).

Therefore at the point the researcher has submitted the federated query, they have approval for the project and the TRE have created the required workflow executor layer.

The researcher submits their query to the GA4GH API ([Figure 3, A](#)) and a process is initiated to confirm this request has come from a researcher that is known and for a project that has been approved. If so, the TES payload is placed into the Submission Layer queue ([Figure 3, B](#)).

In each TRE, there is the TRE Controller layer that has a TRE Agent ([Figure 3, C](#)), that is repeatedly polling the Queue in the the Submission Layer for any jobs assigned to it to process. If there is a job, it can download the TES payload and again it can check permissions against a local TRE specific database, that this request is from an approved researcher and an approved project. If yes, it will then submit the payload to the Hutch Job API ([Figure 3, D](#)) and place the RO-Crate in the airgap storage ([Figure 3, E](#)). In submitting the job for processing, the TRE is in effect approving the payload to be processed.

Hutch will fetch the RO-Crate from the airgap storage ([Figure 3, E](#)), and access the required workflows via the proxy ([Figure 3, F](#)). The proxy manages the difference between what is in the RO-Crate that will reference a workflow repository, like Workflow Hub, and instead redirect the query to the local store ([Figure 3, G](#)). It is the workflow that is then sent to WfExS for processing ([Figure 3, H](#)). At this stage WfExS can access the required containers via the local store ([Figure 3, I](#)) and, for the initial deployment, we only supported workflows that could run against a Postgres database ([Figure 3, J](#)).

At the end of the processing Hutch manages the disclosure process and the egress of the result. It does this initially by notifying the TRE Controller that there is a job that has completed and ready for egress. That in turn will notify a member of the TRE staff to inform them that a request is pending ([Figure 3, K](#)). Once approved by a person, the TRE Controller will authorise Hutch to perform the egress and provide it with a storage location ([Figure 3, E](#)).

The final steps are the wrapping up and completion of the five safes RO-Crate profile and the results returned to the user.

Table 3 summaries the code repositories for TRE-FX stack.

Table 3: TRE-FX stack source code repositories

Submission & Controller	Submission layer (outside TRE) and Controller layer (inside TRE)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DARE-Control • DARE-TREFX-Environment1
Executing agent	Hutch	Hutch
Workflow provenance	Five Safes RO-Crate	5s-crate

Health Data Research (HDR) UK Cohort Discovery Tool

Health Data Research UK is a national Institute in the UK focused on data science in healthcare. One of the key challenges in healthcare is the ability to find the relevant datasets for a study. HDR UK adopted the output from a project called CO-CONNECT³³ in the UK that adopted an existing cohort discovery tool³⁴ developed by the University of Nottingham in partnership with BC Platforms³⁵. This tool allows researchers to construct a query in a product called BC RQuest and TREs install software within their TRE that can pull down the queries from RQuest, run the query, and return a summary count. The tool is proprietary but it does have an API specification.

WfExS-backend

WfExS-backend (Workflow Execution Service */why'fex/*)³⁶ is a high-level workflow orchestrator designed for use in secure computing environments, such as TRE-FX, as well as in other computational backend for container-based workflow execution. It manages, executes, and tracks scientific workflows in isolated environments, designed for data-intensive research with a strong focus on reproducibility and portability.

Key features:

- **Workflow Execution Management:** WfExS-backend delegates the execution of workflows to specialised workflow orchestration engines, such as Nextflow (NFL)³⁷ and Common Workflow Language (CWL)³⁸, fully supporting their domain-specific languages (NFLv2, CWL v1.2).
- **Workflow Run RO-Crate (WRROC)³⁹ Support** for Enhanced Reproducibility: WfExS-backend integrates RO-Crate packaging based on WRROC profiles, granting that workflows, data, and metadata are organised into standardised, self-contained, and easily shareable packages (see section [RO-Crate](#) for more details).

³³ Jefferson E et al. CO-CONNECT, A Hybrid Architecture (CO-CONNECT) to Facilitate Rapid Discovery and Access to Data Across the United Kingdom in Response to the COVID-19 Pandemic: Development Study. 7 June 2022 doi: [10.2196/40035](https://doi.org/10.2196/40035)

³⁴ HDR UK Cohort Discovery tool, <https://www.hdruk.ac.uk/news/hdruk-launches-transformational-new-search-functionality-cohort-discovery/>

³⁵ BC Platforms: Trusted Insights from Data. BC Platforms, 2024, <https://www.bcplatforms.com/>.

³⁶ Jose. M Fernández, et al. FAIR Workflow Execution with WfExS-backend and Workflow Run Crate. BioHackEU23, 28 March 2024, doi: [10.37044/osf.io/7f94w](https://doi.org/10.37044/osf.io/7f94w)

³⁷ Paolo Di Tommaso et al. Nextflow enables reproducible computational workflows. Nature biotechnology. 1 Apr. 2017, doi: [10.1038/nbt.3820](https://doi.org/10.1038/nbt.3820)

³⁸ Common Workflow Language, <https://github.com/common-workflow-language/cwl>

³⁹ Simone Leo et al. Recording provenance of workflow runs with RO-Crate. 9) 10 Sep. 2024, doi: [10.1371/journal.pone.0309210](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0309210)

- **Interoperability with GA4GH TRS and DRS:** Enables WfExS-backend to interact with GA4GH-compliant services and workflow registries (e.g., WorkflowHub⁴⁰) and access data across distributed systems (e.g., DataHub⁴¹).
- **Compute backend flexibility:** Natively integrates with cloud and HPC environments, enabling workflows to run across different infrastructures. Currently Docker⁴², Podman⁴³ and Singularity⁴⁴ are supported.
- **Computational Resource Management:** WfExS-backend controls, limits and reports the resources consumed by complex workflows via the corresponding workflow managers. Additionally, both container images, workflows and inputs might be cached, serving not only to replicability purposes but also resource reusability.
- **Data Provenance and Tracking:** The WfExS-backend gathers containers' metadata to identify unique and persistent references for workflows, container images and inputs (e.g. using canonical commits or container layer identifiers instead of tags, that may change). While workflow engines may fetch some of this information at runtime, they lack specific commands to gather it beforehand or retrieve associated container metadata. These reproducible fingerprints are captured in the *prospective provenance report*, which outlines the blueprint of how data is intended to flow, supporting reproducibility for future re-analysis. Complementarily, retrospective provenance builds on prospective provenance, adding execution metadata such as timestamps, exit values, output sizes and fingerprints, and logs, ensuring traceability and validation during re-analysis.
- **Version Control and Dependency Management:** WfExS-backend detects both the workflow language and the recommended versions of the workflow engines based on the annotations provided by the workflow authors. It also tries to detect all the source files needed by the workflow (in the case of Nextflow workflows) or to generate a compacted version of the workflow (in the case of CWL ones), so that a generated Workflow Run RO-Crate contains both the pointer to the used workflow release and a working snapshot (in case the original one disappears).

4.1.3. TRE-FX setup

The Demonstrator was taken from the previous work of DARE UK TRE-FX project, with additional activities undertaken to adapt it into the ENTRUST Demonstrator. [Figure 4](#) highlights two new components added to the original TRE-FX stack ([Figure 3](#)). A comparison between the HDR UK Cohort Discovery Tool and the GA4GH Beacon provided valuable insights, as these systems utilise distinct design patterns, API specifications, and

⁴⁰ WorkflowHub, <https://workflowhub.eu>

⁴¹ Datahub, <https://datahub.io/>

⁴² Docker Inc. Docker Documentation. Docker, 2024, <https://docs.docker.com>

⁴³ Podman Project. Podman Documentation. Podman, 2024, <https://podman.io>

⁴⁴ Sylabs Inc. Singularity Documentation. Sylabs, 2024, <https://sylabs.io/singularity>

licensing models. The Demonstrator addresses these differences by harmonising responses via the GA4GH TES API. HDR UK Cohort Discovery Tool, supplied by the commercial provider BC Platforms, operates in a proprietary format and uses a polling mechanism to query the service. Conversely, the GA4GH Beacon, an open-source community initiative, uses a posting mechanism to send queries directly to datasets. The following sections summarise the implementation of both network systems.

Figure 4: The stack is exactly the same as [Figure 3](#), it has the two components at the top to cover the RQuest bridge to interact with the HDR Cohort Discovery tool and the Beacon Query. The HDR tool has an API that the RQuest Bridge polls and then submits to the TES API. The Beacon sends out queries to endpoints, therefore, the Hutch Beacon receives the query from the Beacon network and then also submits it to the TES API in the submission layer.

Beacon implementation

Beacon implementation is based on previous work from the BY-COVID project⁴⁵ that developed some of the key components for Beacon implementation over the existing stack. The TRE-FX works by having an external queue ([Figure 4](#), B) which each TRE connects to via an outbound connection. The GA4GH beacon does not operate in a way that is immediately compatible, as it posts the query to a publicly accessible endpoint. Our publicly accessible API endpoint is the GA4GH TES standard, therefore, we created a Beacon to TES standard conversion service (see [table 4](#)), that receives the query in native GA4GH Beacon specification and then converts this into a TES payload ([Figure 4](#), “Hutch Beacon”).

In order to process the GA4GH query, we wrote a workflow hosted in Workflow Hub, called *Beacon workflow* (see [table 4](#)).

Table 4: Source code repositories of the Beacon implementation at TRE-FX

Hutch Beacon Service	GA4GH Beacon to TES converter	Hutch Beacon
Demonstrator Workflow	Run OMOP ⁴⁶ query	Beacon Workflow

HDR UK implementation

The tool from HDR UK uses the BC Platforms RQest tool, and it has an API that allows others to connect to queries that have been submitted. The RQest Bridge ([Figure 4](#), “RQest Bridge”), polls the tool in their native API specification, but then converts this into a TES payload and submits down the TRE-FX stack as normal.

In order to process the BC Platforms query, we wrote a workflow hosted in Workflow Hub, called the *RQest Omop Worker Workflow* (source code at [Table 5](#)).

Table 5: Source code repositories of the HDR UK implementation at TRE-FX

Demonstrator Workflow	Run OMOP query	RQest Omop Worker Workflow
-----------------------	----------------	--

Deployment

Up to this point, the full TRE-FX stack had only been deployed within the context of the original project and only by the teams who developed each component. A first test of the existing documentation was to take all the components and create a full ENTRUST replica.

⁴⁵ BY-COVID project, <https://by-covid.org/>

⁴⁶ OMOP Common Data Model. Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics (OHDSI), <https://ohdsi.github.io/CommonDataModel/>.

The full stack was installed at Nottingham University (UNOTT) and separately in an NHS England Secure Data Environment⁴⁷ with no support from the technical team.

Both were achieved, and a single instance in Nottingham is used as the Demonstrator. This activity helped to capture more requirements for the documentation needs, deployment methods and infrastructure considerations.

4.1.4. Gap Analysis

This analysis aims to summarise the lessons learned from the Demonstrator. It is intended not only to identify potential challenges and evaluate performance under realistic conditions but also to clarify the gaps that need to be addressed. By doing so, the analysis will guide the next development phase, ensuring that improvements align with project goals and meet real-world requirements.

Table 6. Demonstrator gap analysis

Current State	Desired State	Gap	Action Step	Considerations
<i>Deployment</i>				
WfExS-backend is being executed as a host process by Hutch	Gaining portability and control using WfExS-backend container	<i>Deployment of WfExS-backend container</i>	Enabling Hutch for managing WfExS-backend executions via docker containers or singularity	The approach implies a nested container setup, which may require privileged access to Docker daemon, a discouraged practice. Some restrictions could apply to FUSE-binded data volumes
Hutch agent is being executed as a host process	Gaining portability and control implementing a Hutch container	<i>Implementation and deployment of Hutch container</i>	Preparing a Hutch docker image and managing WfExS-backend container-based executions from it.	Again, it entails a nested container setup

⁴⁷ NHS England. *Secure Data Environment: Supporting Safe and Secure Access to NHS Data for Research and Analysis*, <https://digital.nhs.uk>

Current State	Desired State	Gap	Action Step	Considerations
Workflow steps are run as local container instances	Workflow steps are run using a scalable computation facility, which would improve stakeholder adoption	<i>Lack of a scalable container backend orchestrator (e.g. Kubernetes)</i>	Both WfExS-backend and Hutch agent should be extended to integrate the Kubernetes Control API when managing their containers	Either WfExS-backend delegates on the different workflow engines Kubernetes scheduling capabilities (and limitations) of Nextflow and a CWL implementation, or some MITM (man in the middle) software implementation has to be performed to give those capabilities.
Some TRE-FX architecture components cannot be easily deployed or updated	Besides the expected infrastructure (e.g, kubernetes), one command or click installation and update	<i>More portable and automated-build full stack</i>	A common threat was that when assembling existing tools the deployment can be a challenge, with slight changes knocking out the full stack. We must consider how a single click deploy across all tools is possible	Integration tests are needed, both internally (some internal component has been updated) and within the TRE ecosystem (the new deployment can interact with other deployments following the same standards)
<i>User interface</i>				
WfExS-backend is being used through command-line commands	WfExS-backend is integrated and extended, using a stable API, without breaking back-compatibility	<i>WfExS-backend not integrable as a library module due lack of documentation</i>	Hutch should be using WfExS-backend in library mode, which would bypass the need to add some functionality into the core of WfExS-backend.	WfExS-backend is already provided as a python library, yet, clear documentation on usage is to be produced.
No GA4GH WES endpoint is provided either from Hutch or WfExS-backend sides to TRE-FX	A GA4GH WES endpoint which allows different components to use standardised	<i>No standardised way to submit workflow analyses from within TRE-FX architecture</i>	Providing a GA4GH WES API REST envelope around WfExS-backend which should un-marshall requests, call	A separate implementation which uses WfExS-backend in library mode should implement the GA4GH WES endpoint. The

Current State	Desired State	Gap	Action Step	Considerations
	computational workflows		WfExS-backend core, and marshall responses.	features of that implementation should be agreed.
<i>Air Gapping</i>				
WfExS-backend limitations on workflow stage-in are currently covered by Hutch, better integrated with other TRE components	WfExS-backend should stage-in workflows (and dependencies) upon the agreed interfaces	<i>Not standardised protocols for workflow and workflow engines admission, fetching and vetting within the TRE</i>	Either TRE custom WfExS-backend pluggable extensions (<i>i.e.</i> “fetchers”) should be implemented, or standard interfaces are agreed (e.g. local GA4GH TRS and docker registry deployments, or pre-approved WRROC containing all workflow dependencies)	Having WRROC templates of vetted workflows introduces the chicken-and-egg problem of how a new workflow is validated and accepted within TRE-FX, and how the default values of its parameters are initially chosen using scientific criteria. Curators are needed for this task.
<i>RO-Crates</i>				
WfExS-backend supports WRROC for provenance analysis. Hutch completes the tracking by interacting with other TRE components and interoperating with Five Safes RO-Crates	WfExS-backend is able to import and augment Five Safes RO-Crates providing full provenance chain of workflow job processing across TREs	<i>Five Safes RO-Crate support</i>	WfExS-backend should ingest RO-Crates based on Five Safes profiles (or similar) to not require TRE specific agents (<i>i.e.</i> Hutch) to fulfil that role. It implies that the specification internally supports both, BagIt ⁴⁸ archives and SignPosting ⁴⁹ .	Explore to what extent other TRE components require to interoperate with Five Safe RO-Crates for the checking, validating, retrieving, disclosing and publishing job processes.

⁴⁸ BagIt File Packaging Format, *Library of Congress*, 2024, <https://www.loc.gov/standards/bagit>

⁴⁹ Herbert Van de Sompel, et al. Signposting: Expressing Information Resource Relationships on the Web. *arXiv*, 2024, <https://arxiv.org/abs/1702.08374>.

4.1.5. WfExS-backend Extension

To better support the current Demonstrator, the WfExS-backend has been extended to include enhanced functionalities for more refined control over workflow resources, better execution isolation and support for the creation of Workflow Run RO-Crates (WRROCs). These additions are the core of WfExS-backend v1.0 release⁵⁰. Compared to the last version, key updates already tested and validated at the current Demonstrator deployment include:

- **Improved FAIR provenance** is achieved through the usage of CURIEs⁵¹ and URIs (preferable, persistent identifiers) to refer to input datasets, workflows, and containers. These CURIEs and URIs must either be resolvable and fetchable via one of the "*WfExS-backend fetchers*" (customizable, pluggable modules for accessing tools and data repositories), or mapped to a local file path.
- **Isolated execution through a nested containerization** strategy: leveraging the WfExS-backend container, the system supports a nested Singularity-based workflow execution from a WfExS-backend session running within either Singularity, Podman, or Docker instance.
- **Provision of more secure staged working directories:** when a workflow execution is staged on a secure working directory, WfExS-backend binds an encrypted FUSE filesystem for storing all the cloned inputs, workflow, container snapshots, results, and intermediate or transient contents generated from the execution. The encryption key could be provided by the user (e.g. TRE admin or researcher), or generated by WfExS-backend (via Crypt4GH⁵²). It is used to initially encrypt, and later decrypt, the unique symmetric key used for that encrypted working directory. As a side effect, all these contents are not readable by other users of the processing platform, even when the FUSE filesystem is mounted.
- **Support for fine-grained configuration of data shareability** and propagation at dataset-level: The feature is particularly relevant for TREs implementing strict data access models. Now, WfExS-backend implements several flags which restricts the inclusion/reference of input datasets as part of WRROCs, and limits their copies along the different processing stages:
 - “disclosable” flag: can a copy of the dataset be released as a payload of the provenance Workflow Run RO-Crate?
 - “cacheable” flag: can a copy of the dataset be stored in a cache folder to be reused later when needed, or deposited straight on the working directory?
 - “clonable” flag: can the resolved registered dataset be copied to the working directory, or only a symbolic link used?

⁵⁰Jose M. Fernández et al. WfExS-backend. 1.0.0rc0. Zenodo, Set. 2024, doi: [10.5281/zenodo.13821549](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13821549)

⁵¹CURIE Syntax 1.0: A Syntax for Compact URIs. World Wide Web Consortium (W3C), 16 Dec. 2010, <https://www.w3.org/TR/curie/>

⁵²Crypt4GH: Enhancing the Use of Encrypted Data. GA4GH, <https://www.ga4gh.org/>.

- **Support for WRROC export:** provenance of an already staged and/or executed workflow scenario can be exported to a Workflow Run RO-Crate at different levels, so either only minimal details or additional allowed payloads (like snapshots of the workflow, containers and distributable inputs) are included.
- **Wider support for workflow and data staging:** WfExS-backend can load the definition of the execution scenario to be staged (workflow, input parameters, container technology) from (a) YAML-formatted configuration file for new analyses (b) WRROCs and (c) previously staged working directory containing checkpoint files. For this last case, it is also possible to perform replication analyses, providing an additional minimal YAML-formatted configuration file where some of the input parameters are replaced by new ones.

As described in the previous section, the WfExS-backend v1.0 has been installed and tested at TRE-FX setup.

4.2. Future Architecture view

The proposed target architecture builds upon feedback from the initial EOSC-ENTRUST blueprints (WP13, the strategic Drivers (WP7) and the TRE forum (WP10), integrating lessons learned from the current Demonstrator experience. This approach expands the existing setup and focuses on creating a flexible functional unit designed to be easily adopted by distinct TRE setups.

[Figure 5](#) illustrates the high-level architecture of the proposed design, emphasising its core component, the "Workflow Execution Layer." The diagram highlights the interactions between this central module and other TRE and federation services already mapped to components of the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint architecture.

The Workflow Execution Layer is meant to function as an internal TRE component for executing FAIR-compliant workflows in isolated environments, where Five Safe RO-Crates serve as the primary shareable data vehicle. The layer would comprise two main components:

- TES API will offer a standardised GA4GH TES interface, supporting task submission, status tracking, and result retrieval in a RESTful manner.
- WfExS-backend will act as the TES API's backend, and will manage data and software staging (in coordination with other TRE services) and control end-to-end workflow execution within the TRE's compute environment.

Figure 5: Target components architecture of the next release Demonstrator

The numbered arrows in the diagram outline a first version of the sequential steps involved in supporting an “Indirect Query” approach for a federated workflow execution job request. Below is a description of the Five Safes RO-crate flow across the system:

1. Researcher is identified by EOSC-ENTRUST Federation Services
2. Researcher obtains the required permissions to submit a Job Request
3. Researcher creates a Job Request, including all relevant information.
4. Researcher submits the Job Request.
5. After approval, Job Submission Layer accepts the new request.
6. Job Submission Layer creates and pushes a Five Safes RO-Crate associated with the researcher's Job Request to a compliance registry. With the returned URL, the layer composes and submits a Job Request compliant with GA4GH TES including with the crate referred as payload.
7. TRE Job Controller pulls the Job Request and validates it against the Federation Services and the TRE local services.
8. After TRE Job approval, the Job Controller might interact with DMZ to ensure relevant Datasets are available to QMZ's Compute Backend.
9. TRE Job Controller sends the Job Request to the Workflow Execution Layer, who

features a GA4GH TES API.

10. TES API processes the Job Request and sends the corresponding Five Safes RO-Crate to WfExS-backend.
11. WfExS-backend loads the Five Safes RO-Crate and manages data and software staging by interacting with local TRE services.
12. WfExS-backend delegates the execution to the corresponding Workflow Execution Manager (*i.e.* CWL, Nextflow), which will be in charge of deploying and orchestrating the processes at the compute backend. It also checks and gathers information regarding the execution status and/or progress of the different steps for audit purposes.
13. Compute Backend accesses the Intermediary Store and creates the Output data.
14. WfExS-backend generates the corresponding Five Safes RO-Crate capturing the workflow process and the outputs provenance.
15. TES API composes the Job Response compliant with GA4GH TES including the job Five Safes RO-Crate.
16. Job Controller validates the Job Response.
17. If required, Job Controller interacts with the DMZ to store Job Outputs.
18. Job Controller returns the Job Response to the Job Submission Service.

4.2.1. Mapping to EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint

The following table ([Table 7](#)) provides a summary mapping of the early release of the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint architecture component⁵³ to the corresponding components in the Demonstrator ([Figure 4](#)), showing minimal gaps at the high-level architectural level. This mapping focuses on components essential to achieving the Demonstrator's objectives and highlights key functional requirements expected to be met by these components.

Table 7. Mapping of target Demonstrator's architecture components to EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint

EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint Component		Corresponding Demonstrator Component	Demonstrator specific requirements
Query Management Zone (QMZ)			
Job Controller	=	Job Controller	Internal TRE component that should interact with 5s RO-Crates for its Validation, Ingestion and Sign-off

⁵³ EOSC-ENTRUST Deliverable D13.4: [Year one version of EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint & Interoperability Framework](#)

Job Executor	=	Workflow Executor Layer	Core component of the reference implementation of this Demonstrator
N/A	≈	Intermediary Storage	Workflow Executor Layer requires a locally accessible storage, typically an Intermediary Storage (e.g. GA4GH DRS). The direct QMZ - SDZ relationship described in the should consider it.
HPC	=	Compute Backend	Should permit supported container engines (<i>i.e.</i> docker, podman, singularity)
Artefact cache	=	Software cache	Typically, pre-approved container images and workflows
Job submission service	=	Submission Layer	Should validate user-submitted RO-Crates, register them and submit TES-compliant job requests to the relevant TRE. TRE job pulling mechanism recommended.
Software service	=	WorkflowHub (for Workflows)	Should support RO-Crates and is recommend to be TRS-compliant
Federation Services			
Identity provider	=	Identity provider	Assuming a federated AAI
N/A	≠	Disclosure Procedure	Minimal Disclosure Procedure agreement at the federation level required
Accounting	=	Accounting	
Data objects (<i>when new job request is submitted</i>)			
Query Indirect	=	Job Request	GA4GH TES <i>tesTask</i> data model containing: - a <i>tesInput</i> whose "URL" is the persistent URL storage of the Five Safe RO-Crate workflow request - a <i>tesOutput</i> whose "URL" is the persistent URL storage of a Five Safe RO-Crate workflow process

Response	=	Response	TES <i>Task</i> identifier for asynchronous tracking of execution
----------	---	----------	---

5. Results

This deliverable presents the Deployable Demonstrator of Digital Objects & Workflows Developments based on the DARE-UK implementation. Applied to federated data discovery, it has demonstrated its use to receive a Beacon and a query from the HDR UK Cohort Discovery tool, without changing any of the underlying infrastructure, but by simply switching the workflow that is required to processing the query ([Figure 6](#) and [Figure 7](#)).

University of Nottingham
UK | CHINA | MALAYSIA

Beacon

About

This Beacon uses the GA4GH Beacon v2 API specification and is provided by the Centre for Health Informatics and Digital Research Service at the University of Nottingham. Beacon filters can be used to query a backend OMOP database of synthetic COVID-19 patient EHRs (electronic health records). The Beacon will return **true** or **false** to indicate if the filters have been observed in any individuals.

Query

Select filtering terms: ✓

- Gender:F - FEMALE
- Gender:M - MALE
- Race:2 - Asian
- Race:3 - Black or African American
- Race:5 - White

Search Clear

Figure 6: The Nottingham Beacon interface used to create queries

Cohorts Add new cohort

History New Query

Collections Select genes Add Filter New Query

Group 1: AHD Asthma Add Filter

Count details

Collection	External ID	Total ↓	Status	Relative
HAB-2	Link name	1234	job done	1234 100.00%
M2_Min 10	Link name	0	Time out	0.00%

Figure 7: The search interface from the HDR Cohort Discovery Tool (supplied by BC Platforms) interacting with the TRE-FX stack

The Demonstrator can be installed and has been installed within the SAIL databank⁵⁴ and a test installation within a NHS England Secure Data Environment. Additionally, the latest

⁵⁴SAIL databank, <https://saildatabank.com>

WfExS-backend release was integrated and successfully validated within such a setup. The learnings from those using and those deploying the Demonstrator have been the basis for the reported gap analysis, which assesses the strengths and limitations of the current environment and establishes a clear roadmap for ongoing technical development.

Along with the current Demonstrator, a target architecture for the next-year release Demonstrator is presented. It shows good alignment with the highest-level architecture described in the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint v.1, providing a solid basis for further iterations specifying interfaces and data object models. The mapping of Demonstrator's components highlighted also the dependencies on critical Federated Services and TRE components which, as discussed in the next section, may require extension to fully support the proposed approach - particularly, the Five Safes RO-Crate.

WP19 has materialised these efforts in a number of related publications, presentations, and software releases or specifications, all listed at [Appendix: Results](#).

6. Discussion

The current Demonstrator has successfully validated the feasibility and practical value of the proposed approach. It has confirmed that the reference implementation can operate securely within TREs while meeting critical interoperability and compliance standards that enabled scaling to a federated infrastructure and improved automation of key internal TRE processes. Still, it has raised some technical and interoperability points, particularly relevant when the approach is expected to be adopted by an heterogeneous set of TREs.

Five Safes RO-Crates demonstrated the ability to produce **FAIR-compliance evidence of TRE usage** for workflow-based processing, while adhering to strict data governance requirements. Yet, it implies the adoption of the standard by other key internal TRE and federation services (*e.g.* TRE controller and Submission Layer) in order to provide an end-to-end tracking of the whole process and effectively validating and approving job requests as well as data assets exchanges according to the RO-Crate metadata. It is important to note, however, that RO-Crates are a metadata collection structure and should not be overused in the architecture design, as other standards like GA4GH TES and WES are more suitable for certain use cases.

Of course, the approach taken is not infinitely scalable, as we had to draft two converters and two workflows to support the two different federated approaches. One of our use-cases was even just converting between two GA4GH standards (*i.e.* Beacon and TES). This approach was taken to demonstrate the power of common standards, and we hope and expect that there is **more alignment to existing international standards**. Therefore, we would suggest that going forward there is more alignment on these standards across TREs, so that they can be adopted more universally.

Additionally, enabling compute federation goes hand in hand with the adoption of TRE FAIR-compliant data management models, where datasets are described as FAIR resources using persistent identifiers. Further extending the use of standards for tools and data management (e.g. GA4GH TRS or GA4GH DRS) will help enforce such practices.

7. Next steps

Working towards the next release of the Demonstrator, the following steps will guide WP19 efforts during the following year:

1. **Analyse the requirements of the next release Demonstrator design:** Conduct a detailed analysis of the Five Safe RO-Crate workflow across the system and its interactions with Demonstrator components to ensure all specification-defined processing phases are met.
2. **Develop and test the next release Demonstrator:** Use insights from the gap analysis as a roadmap for guiding the next development phase, aligning with the target architecture. Implement the next release in the DARE-UK TRE-FX as the primary testing and validation TRE setup.
3. **Enhance Workflow Orchestrator Capabilities:** Based on the previous phase, continue developing the WfExS-backend to improve metadata capture by supporting the generation and consumption of Five Safes RO-Crates. Implement resource fetchers to broaden integration with local TRE services and agreed-upon standardised interfaces.
4. **Expand and Validate Five Safes RO-Crate interoperability use:** Demonstrate the metadata collection standard across diverse use cases, covering multiple data governance models and data management systems.
5. **Use Case Development:** Define a detailed use case in collaboration with EOSC-ENTRUST Drivers to showcase federated compute capabilities in real-world TRE applications.
6. **Stakeholder Engagement:** Increase engagement through comprehensive documentation, best-practice recommendations for FAIR compliance, and training materials to improve usability and adoption by TRE administrators and, importantly, their end users.

8. Impact

While it may be early to observe the full impact of this initial Demonstrator, developing a reference implementation for workflow-based federated computation based on robust interoperability standards has already raised interest among other European infrastructure initiatives. This is the case for the **Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI)**, which seeks to create a network of national-level European TREs (or Secure Processing Environments,

SPEs). While there are significant differences in the specifics, we share several technical commonalities, such as the adoption of GA4GH standards—specifically TES and WES—and alignment with EHDS requirements for the secondary use of health data and the constraints this may entail.

I. Appendix: Results

Publications

- Gonzalo E, Codó L, Fernandez JM *et al.* **Five safes workflow RO-Crate and WfExS.** Closing the gap of federated analysis and Trusted Research Environments (TREs) in the health data context [version 1; not peer reviewed]. *F1000Research* 2024, **13**(ELIXIR):550 (Poster) (<https://doi.org/10.7490/f1000research.1119724.1>)
- Simone Leo, Michael R. Crusoe, Laura Rodríguez-Navas, Raül Sirvent, Alexander Kanitz, Paul De Geest, Rudolf Wittner, Luca Pireddu, Daniel Garijo, José M. Fernández, Iacopo Colonnelli, Matej Gallo, Tazro Ohta, Hirotaka Suetake, Salvador Capella-Gutierrez, Renske de Wit, Bruno de Paula Kinoshita, Stian Soiland-Reyes (2024): **Recording provenance of workflow runs with RO-Crate.** *PLOS One* 19(9):e0309210 <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0309210>

Workshops and presentations

- Digital Transformation to support FAIR, workflows and federated analytics, *EOSC-ENTRUST Evaluation & Adoption Workshop*, Helsinki, 24th & 25th September 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13935169>
- WfExS Summer Days, Barcelona, 6-8th August 2024. https://docs.google.com/document/d/1AKS7Am6YSMeLuNzGqtxtzETadAhTeYQDu_mpy_U9DIAA/edit?tab=t.0
- ELIXIR All Hands Meeting 2024 (AHM2024), Uppsala, Sweden. Tim Beck, Stian Soiland-Reyes (2024): Potential of ELIXIR cloud methods in EOSC-ENTRUST and HDR UK. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11654733>
- 17 Sep 2024: GA4GH Connect plenary: Tim Beck “*TRE-FX Platform for federated analysis across Trusted Research Environments (TREs)*” https://docs.google.com/document/d/1augQzdtcNEKaqD2Mfmvw1s1cK-_4Zwka/e_dit

Software and specifications

- [WfExS-backend 1.0.0rc0](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13821549) released <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13821549>
- [Workflow Run RO-Crate profiles 0.5](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12158562) released <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12158562>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12159311>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12160782>

Community enhancement

- Creation of the WfExS channel at ELIXIR Slack
- Creation of the “WfExS Community” regular meetings